

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – Digital Twin Enabled Multi Physics Simulation and Model Matching

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document

Title:

DIGITAL TWIN ENABLED MULTI PHYSICS SIMULATION AND MODEL MATCHING USE CASE

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

Contextualizing information between multi-physics simulations and vaster information constructs such as digital twins. 3D geometries, measurements, simulations, and asset management coexist in such information constructs.

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Finished

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Introduction:

Enabling meaningful simulations within new human-infrastructure interfaces such as Digital twins is paramount. Accessing the power of simulation opens manifold new ways for observation, understanding, analysis and prediction of numerous scenarios to which the asset may be faced. As a result, managers can access countless ways of acquiring synthetic data for eventually taking better, more informed decisions. This use case document is conceived as a fundamental part of this endeavour. This use case is aimed at contextualizing information between multi-physics simulations and vaster information constructs such as digital twins. 3D geometries, measurements, simulations, and asset management coexist in such information constructs.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

TUB, UPC

Partners:

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Handling (can be edited based on preference):

N/A

Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

N/A

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Multi-Physics Simulations and Digital Twins Matching
Goal	Having more informed decisions with enriched synthetic data by matching simulations and measurements.
Description	Contextualization of the information between multi-physics simulations and vaster information constructs such as digital twins. 3D geometries, measurements, simulations, and asset management coexist in such information constructs.
Input Data	There are different inputs such as sensors, images, computer visions and remote sensing and simulation results. Real-time data of these activities are collected from the construction site and used as input data.
Sequence of actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Measuring data from IOT and doing simulations and creating verifiable and validated data. 2. Enter Inputs from measurements and simulations 3. Matching the measurements data with simulations data 4. Having an enhanced Digital Twin of the construction project
Primary actors	Design Engineers, Infrastructure Managers
Secondary actors	Project Managers, Civil Engineers, Civil Engineering Companies
Pre-conditions	Adequate amount of production data of the site
Trigger	
Post-conditions	
Frequency of use	Real Time
Support planned for	ASHVIN
UC Created by	

Date of last update	
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Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

This proposed document describes the conception of matching the simulations synthetic data and measurements from Internet of things data and their background. The document provides guidance for the generation of adequate initial conditions of the assets to be used during their life span using a Digital Twin basis.

Objectives:

This document is targeted to design engineers and infrastructure managers that intend to develop simulations within digital twin systems for structural analysis, be it general digital twin platforms or specific management tools to make use of digital twin data.

Additionally, the report is targeted towards IT managers and R&I professionals that plan to implement specific digital twin systems and solutions for specific maintenance & operation purposes.

In this document, applications on democases are described. Laboratory tests on structural elements, detailed flows from sensor to simulations, computationally tractable reduced-order methods, full-order methods, and model calibration actions are described taking inspiration from demo sites one, six, seven and nine from the Ashvin project.

One of the applications that is largely described in this document is related to load tests of assets. Load tests provide an ideal scenario for the development of Verifiable & Validated simulations of the structural behavior of infrastructure systems. With sufficient layers, the information construct Digital Twin developed at this stage can be deemed as being an initial digital birth of the studied bridges. All efforts devoted to the development of a series of load tests on real bridges by owners, managers, construction firms and academia are put together to generate an archaic yet complete information construct. It is considered that in today's standards, even archaic versions of digital births of bridges developed will provide meaningful data for owners, managers, construction firms and academia in the years to come.

2.3 Overall Process:

The overall process for the Digital Twin Enabled Multi Physics Simulation And Model Matching use case is presented in Figure 2. According to the project and set up activities the scenario configuration is prepared by acquiring environmental conditions. After these steps, Matching can be started. In the end, results are shown with the visualisation software. These results can be evaluated easily and if they are not satisfied, the user should go back to the scenario configuration again. During all these activities, the outputs of sensors from construction sites are accumulated into the database.

Figure 2 Process Map

Implementation on #1 Bridges for high-speed railways in Spain

To ensure structural performance and durability of a building or infrastructure, the mechanical properties of the materials must roughly match the values assumed at the design stage. As concrete is a heterogeneous mixture, the uncertainty of its mechanical properties increases, therefore, calibrating a realistic state of the material may be crucial in singular infrastructures such as bridges. For the post-tensioned slab of Viaducto La Plata, one of the bridges of Demo 1, a calibration of the elastic Young's modulus was necessary. From measurements, it is possible by performing reverse engineering to infer more realistic values based on strain measures acquired during the load test. The Young's modulus of the concrete changes over time, thus, predicting a reliable value is key to properly checking the structural performance of a bridge, comparing measured and simulated deflections and strains. Viaducto La Plata is a hyperstatic 4-spanned concrete bridge and is part of the Madrid– Badajoz highspeed railway. It is located near the cross of El Tajo River. Fig. 3 shows the location and the overview of the bridge.

Figure 3 Location and overview of La Plata Viaduct

The lengths of the inner and outer spans are 32.0 and 25.0 meters respectively. The cross section of the bridge's deck is a continuous post-tensioned voided slab of width 14 meters and height 2 meters. Fig. 4 presents front-views as well as the cross section of the bridge. The construction stage of La Plata Viaduct ended. To approve the initiation of the operational stage, a load test was required.

The structural analysis model to simulate the multi-physics of the bridge and check the executed load test is based on a numerical model of nonlinear and time-dependent analysis for three dimensional reinforced and prestressed concrete (Marí 2000). The mathematical model implements frame finite elements with six degrees of freedom per node. These elements are discretized into filaments, with each having a length and prismatic cross-section that are defined by their area and position relative to the sectional local axes and are associated with a specific concrete or steel (Fig. 6).

Figure 4 Longitudinal and cross section of La Plata Viaduct

Figure 5 Load test of La Plata bridge and a sample of collected sensor data

Figure 6 Filament frame element (Source: Mari A, 2000)

Strain compatibility exists between all materials belonging to a given cross-section. A perfect bond is assumed. The principle of plane strain is applied for mechanical and non-mechanical strains. The constitutive models for concrete, active and passive reinforcement, include the rheology of the materials and implement uniaxial stress-strain principles. Loads are assigned to nodes at specific instants, allowing the introduction of load increments and enabling a step-by-step analysis over time. Prestressing loads are applied using an equivalent load vector, defined by balancing the forces of the arrangements of the tendons. This numerical model was the basis for the existing computer program called CONS, which is routinely used for research at the Technical University of Catalonia (Bairán & Marí 2007, Marí et al. 2003, Chacón et al. 2007)

To accurately represent multi-physics simulations within the Digital Twin of an asset, the capabilities of CONS are being leveraged to a powerful graphical environment, using Rhino and Grasshopper parametric software, where discretization of complex cross-sections is possible, enabling a direct construction of fiber-based models. The shape of the bridge cross section, the number of filaments for discretization, the constitutive models of the materials, the pre-stressing loads and tendons, and the internal loads are set up on a visual programming script, enabling a parametric structural analysis, where any changes in the input data will generate a dynamic change in the results, facilitating the calibration of materials' properties or loads. Fig.7 shows the assembly and results of the parametric fiber-based model of La Plata Viaduct's cross section.

Figure 7 Parametric fibre-based model of La Plata Viaduct cross section

During the load test of a bridge, strains are measured to check the structural behavior. However, to verify if the collected data is within the acceptable range, it is required to perform predictive simulations assuming the mechanical properties of the material specified in the project documentation. Given that the concrete is a heterogeneous mix, there may be significant differences between the real and the assumed rheological material properties.

A fiber-based model of the cross section of the bridge (see Fig. 8) allows the matching of the measured strains at the exact location of the sensor, with the strain of the corresponding fiber. Then, by implementing reverse engineering, it is possible to calibrate the elastic young's modulus of the concrete, enabling more precise simulations and improving the verification of the structure's performance, supporting the decision of allowing the initiation of the operational phase.

Figure 8. Sensor location and the corresponding filament to match strains

Implementation on #6 Office Buildings in Barcelona, Spain

The Digital Twin paradigm implies an active connection between the virtual and the real realms. Ideally, data from sensors must flow properly in a digital system to feed a virtual representation of a building or infrastructure. During the construction stage, it is of interest to continuously verify the structural behaviour of an asset with real data acquired at the site. Real data embedded within the simulations provide more realistic results and increase confidence on the construction evolution.

This application shows a detailed flow of data from sensors (temperature) embedded in fresh concrete that feed a structural analysis model. The asset corresponds to an office building widely described (Posada et al. 2022). The process provides a way to verify the allowable deflections of the structural elements depending on the evolution of the concrete compressive strength at early ages, estimated through the maturity index method. As a result, construction managers can get reliable information for decision-making on activities such as early formwork removal.

Maturity refers to the progression of physical properties in concrete during the hydration process, including the evolution of strength. The commonly used maturity method, defined by ASTM C1074, assumes a non-linear correlation between concrete temperature and the rate of the development of the material properties. This method provides quick data without the need for sample transportation or crushing scheduling, but it does require calibration and is dependent on the concrete mix. Additionally, the model cannot be extended to significant changes in the mix between concrete batches.

The testbeds of this example are developed for Demo 6, a concrete building under construction in the Poble Nou district of Barcelona. Fig. 9 shows the render and the BIM model of the office building, highlighting the premises where actions were allowed in the collaboration with the construction company.

Figure 9 MILE Ávila office building render and BIM model (Provided by BIS structures)

Hardware modules were developed at the Laboratory of Digital Models for Structures and Construction (LMDEC) at UPC for data acquisition, allowing customization of the data flow. To

collect data from long-spanned slabs, two types of temperature sensors were used. Two thermocouple K-type sensors with a range from 0°C to 400°C and an accuracy of $\pm 2.2^{\circ}\text{C}$, were connected to a MAX6675 module that converted analog signals to digital. The other type of sensor was a DS18B20, a waterproof digital sensor that communicates through a Wire-1 protocol to read temperatures between -55°C to 125°C with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. Power banks of 5000mAh were used to supply energy, and the sensors data was saved on an SD card for subsequent processing. The components were connected and synchronized to an ESP32 System on Chip module through the Arduino platform. These hardware modules are cost-effective and have open prototyping functionalities. All codes were developed by the authors of this deliverable.

During concrete pouring, access to the slab was restricted, and sensors were embedded fully in the concrete mix only in the allowed areas. In new sites, there is room for improvement in terms of the number and placement of sensors to collect more specific and reliable data. In this case, due to site restrictions, only a limited amount sensors were mounted, which helped prototyping the whole pipeline of information from sensor-to-simulation.

The structure dimensions are: for the post-tensioned maximum span 15.60 m plus a cantilever of 4.40 m, while the transverse direction spans 5.40 m. The cross-section height is 50.0 cm. Fig. 10 shows the location of the sensors and the obtained results during hours of measuring the temperature evolution while the material hardened.

Figure 10 Collection of data, sensors location and measures acquired

After data collection, hardware modules were removed, and measures stored in the SD cards were saved on a local PC as CSV files. Then, this data was imported to the parametric software Grasshopper, where a developed Python script estimates the maturity index and the concrete compressive strength evolution with calibrated data for the specific concrete mix, as shown in Fig 11.

Figure 11 Maturity index and compressive strength estimation from temperature data within Grasshopper

Once the concrete compressive strength evolution at early ages is estimated, a structural analysis model can be performed using the predicted material property within the same parametric environment. At the moment of implementation at the end of 2021, Karamba 3D (2023), a structural analysis plug-in available in Grasshopper was used. First, the concrete material properties are set with the estimated compressive strength as input, calibrating the actual elastic young modulus according to the maturity of the concrete. Material properties of the module of the structural model were fed as shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 12 Concrete material properties with estimated compressive strength (Karamba 3D)

After the concrete properties were defined, the structural model of the corresponding slab was constructed and assembled by the means of the solver (Karamba 3D at that time) as Fig. 13 shows.

Figure 13 Karamba 3D model assembly for the simulation of deflections

Maximum deflections can be obtained as well as stresses at the slab. Technical supervisors or construction managers can get information based on site measurements that feed valuable models on a regular basis. More informed decisions of, for instance, the removal of the formwork or check the quality of the slab casting task can be taken.

Implementation on #7 Bridges In Highway Network In Castellbisbal, Catalonia, Spain

Composite bridges are prevalent and offer the benefits of both concrete and steel structures, leading to cost-effective and efficient solutions. Typically, these bridges consist of concrete slabs supported by steel plate or box girders. The beams of these structures are often made up of welded steel plates with transversal and longitudinal stiffeners, prioritizing material efficiency, weight, and cost in the design. However, this design can result in slender steel plates that are susceptible to buckling under certain stress levels. Buckling could lead to out-of-plane deformation, which would adversely impact the bridge's overall structural integrity.

In the design phase, sophisticated full-order numerical models are commonly used to forecast occurrences of plate buckling or other instability-related phenomena. Theoretical assumptions are made concerning the initial imperfections of steel plates prior to construction. Nonetheless, the post-construction "as-built" configuration of the plates is infrequently utilized to confirm these assumptions, and its transformation over time is not observed. The question to ask in this application is: How does information flow from measurements to geometrically and materially nonlinear simulations with initial imperfections?

This application aims to infer about the flow of information between simulations developed with advanced commercial Software and automated procedures for incorporating both BIM geometries and actual measurements from the site. The study seeks to perform structured and systematic evaluations of plates, stiffeners, diaphragms, or other asset subsets that are related to the structure stability.

To integrate bridge information into larger information constructs, utilizing open BIM standards such as the Industry Foundation Class (IFC) (ISO 2018) is crucial. In terms of the incorporation of measurements, it entails developing semi-automated processes for identifying the initial imperfections of steel plates and subsequently integrating these geometries into advanced inelastic FE simulations for structural analysis at various levels.

The example is based on the PR-04-B015 bridge, located in the national highway network surrounding the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona (Spain). It links two of the main highways in the network: the AP-7 Highway (heading North) and the A-2 Road (Heading West). The PR-04-B015 bridge is a crucial connection point between these two highways, providing commuters with a bypass to circumvent the metropolitan area's suburbs during the transition from north-south to east-west corridors, and vice versa. As a result, the bridge has become a strategic asset for the transportation of goods from Catalonia to Northern Europe. In September 2021, the bridge was opened to traffic, and it has an approximate length of 846 meters. Shown in Fig. 14, the bridge comprises a continuous horizontally curved composite beam that spans a river (Llobregat), a creek (Rubi), various roads, and railway lines. The bridge is divided into two viaducts, one for each driving direction, with each viaduct consisting of 12 spans of varying lengths supported by concrete piers. The cross-section is made up of a steel box section with a variable web height ranging from 3.5 to 5.0 meters, along with a concrete slab with a width that varies between 11.50 and 17.00 meters. The steel box contains transversal and longitudinal stiffeners and diaphragms.

Figure 14. Location and general view of PR-04-B015 bridge

The original bridge design project was completed many years ago, during a time when digital tools and BIM were not sufficiently developed. Most of the bridge's information was stored in pdf files, containing all the relevant details in the form of deliverables and 2D drawings. A comprehensive 3D geometrical model had to be generated. The BIM model was developed according to the IFC open standard, which, in its latest release, permits modelling bridge constitutive parts assigned with a geometric representation, physical properties, and additional semantic information. As illustrated in Fig. 15, the developed model comprises detailed representations of bridge plates, slabs, piles, and stiffeners.

Figure 15. From drawings to IFC accessible geometries

Measurements on the bridge have included, among others, laser scanning. Laser scanning is a technique for capturing reality that produces large point clouds representing the 3D geometry of objects with high accuracy. A point cloud is a disordered set of points that include their coordinates (x_i, y_i, z_i) in a specific coordinate system, as well as other properties that determine the colour and type of surface being scanned. Laser scanners are widely available in the market and are high-performance devices that can capture the geometry of large structures with sub-millimetre accuracy within minutes. However, the primary challenge with this technique is processing the point clouds, which usually comprise millions of unstructured points requiring abstraction of geometrical features. In demo 7, during a given episodic scanning process, two measurements are taken from different points of view in order to capture the whole geometry of the steel box of the bridge. Each measurement takes 30 minutes and generates a point cloud representing a 360 view from the device standpoint with a density of one point every 3mm at a distance of 10m. Both measurements are co-registered into the same reference system using 7 spherical targets placed on fixed points on the ground. As a result of the co-registration process, a single point cloud is obtained containing over 100 million points. Figures 16 and 17 shows an example of the point cloud resulting from the scanning process in which the spheres and the positions of each measurement are marked. During the first measurement, the position of the spherical targets is precisely marked in order to replicate the measurement throughout the years. A total of 4 seasonal episodic scans have been performed until the development of this report. The first scan was taken on March 2022, the second on July 2022, the third on September 2022 and the last in January 2023. Two more episodes are planned in 2023.

Figure 16. Final point cloud after the registration process. The position of the scanner and spherical target is highlighted.

Figure 17. Geometrical model and pointcloud after the registration process.

Subsequently, the scans and its as-designed geometrical model are aligned to the same coordinate system. Two automated data pipelines have been created. The first pipeline involves two steps to streamline and simplify the point cloud. Initially, the point cloud is cropped using the bounding box of the bridge area being studied (as shown in Fig. 18-A). Then, voxel subsampling is employed to decrease the point cloud's size, where points in each voxel are combined into a single averaged point. This approach significantly reduces the point cloud's weight, making it more suitable for demanding computational processes. The second pipeline relates the reduced point cloud to each steel plate in the bridge steel box girder's geometrical model. The point clouds are segmented utilizing the geometrical model's oriented bounding boxes for each individual subpanel (refer to Fig. 18-B).

Figure 18. A: bounding box used to reduce the pointcloud to points contained in the region of study. B: Pointcloud segmentation using oriented bounding boxes of the box girder sub-panels

As a result, point clouds of specific steel plates can be retrieved under request of the user. This is a crucial aspect since this automated process provides a way of systematic addition of new measured information to the system of the bridge and allows linking individually the as-designed geometry in the model with as-built information provided by the point cloud at global and local levels. Fig. 19 shows how, for a given plate, seasonal episodes of point clouds are available and usable.

Figure 19. Multiple scans (M1 to M4) result in overlaid pointclouds that are associated with the elements of the Bridge

It is interesting to compare the differences between the as-built point clouds and the as-designed surface of the geometrical model. To calculate the deviation, the perpendicular distance vector was computed between the measured points and the surface of their corresponding sub-panel in the model. The outcomes are shown in Fig. 20, indicating four episodic measurements. Deviations for measurements taken in March and September (under similar environmental conditions) have comparable patterns, while measurements taken in January and July have different configurations of deviation distributions (Chacón et al. 2022b). The previously presented global deviation analysis captured the initial imperfections of the steel box girder's sub-panels. Interpolating the corresponding points, a new as-built surface was calculated for each panel. These surfaces can be saved and queried with varying levels of granularity and subsequently used for non-linear FE analysis.

The developed procedure facilitates the generation of models at various levels. As a result, during operation, different types of numerical models may be requested (according to different complexity levels shown in Fig. 21). Namely, one can request: i) Instability Eigenvalue analysis of isolated plates, ii) inelastic analysis of stiffened plates (partial strips or full webs) iii) cross-sectional analysis of the composite bridge considering the full section at given locations or iv) full advanced inelastic analysis of the whole asset (which may be computationally intractable nowadays though). In the following, brief discussions of the developments in this example are shown.

Figure 20. Results of the deviation analysis conducted on the bridge span for all the scans up to date

Figure 21. Different levels of available as-built information, from full sections to single web sub-panels

The geometrical models store metadata and information concerning all elements, including the geometrical configurations of both stiffened bottom flanges and webs. The IFC model records all

necessary details about the girder, such as thicknesses, widths, heights, stiffener dimensions, and locations. From this model, users can choose specific panels and retrieve necessary information to conduct plate buckling analysis. Earlier versions of these models employed EBPlate (EBPlate, CTICM, 2007), software that predicts the Eigenvalues and Eigenshapes of in-plane loaded stiffened plates. Fig. 22 displays a selected stiffened web plate exposed to bending, compression, and shear stresses, with results aiding structural modellers in understanding this web portion's stability behavior. The simulations rely on discretization and Fourier series and Fig. 22 also illustrates the outcomes obtained using the open-source Software EBPlate. The platform's current development emphasizes integrating these results at the precise panel location under investigation.

Figure 22. Stability analysis of a longitudinally stiffened partial web

Subsequently, geometrical configurations of both stiffened bottom flanges and webs are stored and processed. These realistic shapes can activate different levels of simulation models. To assess the accuracy and realism of these models that rely on imperfect plates, GMNI analyses were performed on these partial strips. Fig. 23 depicts a linear perturbation analysis of a strip of the web experiencing pure compression. Abaqus Simulia (Simulia 2013) was used to analyse a region between longitudinal stiffeners. Boundary conditions are assumed to be simply supported at this level. Using this Eigenshape as the starting imperfection for advanced inelastic analysis enables numerical solutions for evaluating its sensitivity. The magnitude of these imperfections is always a concern for designers (Chacón et al. 2009). Fig. 24 illustrates a plot that explores the sensitivity to the magnitude of this imperfection, which is related to the Eigenshape.

Figure 23. Eigenvalue analysis of isolated panels.

Figure 24. Sensitivity of the magnitude of imperfection on the load bearing (pure compression)

Structural analysis of isolated stiffened plates but in this case, using realistic imperfections have also been addressed for different episodes. While modelling, special care must be taken with the boundary conditions of the edges to avoid local failure in those regions. The resulting imperfect surfaces require detailed meshing. Small deviations on the surface imply that meshes must generally be unstructured. In some cases, sizes and elements are conditioned by the meshing algorithms. Additionally, special attention must be given to contact regions between elements in the IFC model (for example, between the plates and the stiffeners) which, due to the small deviations introduced, generate small gaps that condition the quality and usability of the meshes and, thus, may require a human-in-the-loop re-modelling process for those specific regions (Fig. 25). The hitherto used data transfer files between surfaces (fitted from point clouds) and FE-friendly meshes are serialized in STEP, a standardized 3D model exchange format that is widely recognized by computer-aided engineering software (STEP-file, ISO 10303-21). Fig. 26 shows an unstructured FE- mesh developed with a medial axis mesh generator.

Figure 25. Imperfect contact between 'as-built' surfaces derived from the pointcloud measurements and 'perfect' stiffeners from the model

Figure 26. Mesh generated from surfaces fitted to the point cloud measurements

Subsequently, Fig. 27 shows advanced full order nonlinear models developed based on the realistic initial conditions. A detailed assessment of the ultimate load capacity of specific plates or vaster models can then be activated by the user.

Figure 27. Full-order GMNIA models based on seasonal imperfections.

In order to visualize these results in the digital twin platform, information must be encapsulated in a JSON format and send back to the corresponding service defined in the data architecture depicted in section 1.4. From measurements to advanced models, this example of application provides a pipeline of information that can benefit maintenance plans. For instance, regular tracking of the shape of the bridge as well as regular visual inspections together can help managers to plan more carefully maintenance plans with more detailed levels of prioritization. The implementation of the results within the Ashvin platform are expected to be included in the final version of MatchFEM at the end of the project.

Implementation on #9 Sport Stadium Roof Structure Munich, Germany

Cable nets are a type of tensile structure that are stabilized by a pre-stress rather than by bending stiffness. They can be configured in multiple ways to enhance their height and load performance. They can also accommodate different geometries, such as doubly curved or planar surfaces. A prominent example of cable nets in European architecture is the Plexiglas-clad roof of the 1972 Munich Olympic Stadium, which spans 74800 square meters with doubly curved cable nets. However, they also present a challenge for the design, construction, and operation phases, as the force distribution along the net is difficult to determine precisely.

The main cables at those structures are either strand bundles or fully locked steel cables. The cable forces are large, and the cable diameters range from 82 mm to 182 mm. A direct measurement of forces would require unpinning the cables and using hydraulic jacks or cable tension meters. This would involve invasive and costly procedures that are not practical to be established by managers on a regular basis. In demo 9, which corresponds to Olympia Stadion, the access to the site was restricted and only contact-less remote sensing techniques were allowed. Therefore, indirect measurement methods were needed to estimate the cable forces. In this matter, remote sensing using laser scanners was an alternative non-invasive solution to obtain valuable geometrical measurements from which the cable forces could be derived. In order to gain understanding of the use of such measurements, a laboratory-scale reduced model was developed as a testbed of methods for understanding its application of at the Munich Olympic Stadium.

A terrestrial laser scanner was used in the lab to obtain a point cloud from which the movement of the cable net nodes at different load configurations was captured. Then, computationally tractable numerical models were fed with the captured node configuration to obtain a real-time view of the cable force distribution on the net.

For the design of the net reduced-scale model, The Force Density Method (FDM) was used. Details about the algorithm can be found in Linkwitz (2014) Nodes connecting the ends of cable elements were arranged in two levels, using compressive clamps connected by a frictionless bolt, to allow relative rotations of the cables attached to them. The net is anchored to two “C-shaped” steel beams. A steel mast is fixed is used to give some lift to some of the net anchors. Holes in the mast and beams enable the connection of the cable net by using hooks. The resulting mock-up and details are shown in Fig. 28.

Figure 28. Prestressed cable net

The cable net mock-up as built point cloud can be obtained with a single measurement from a TLS placed below the net. The resulting pointcloud contained considerable amount of noise in the zones surrounding the cables due to their reduced section size. However, the geometry of the nodes was successfully captured. Fig. 29 displays the result of a single scan of the mock-up cable net.

Figure 29. Initial TLS scan of the prestressed cable net mock-up

Point clouds need to be processed to obtain the points representing the as-built position of the nodes. The regions of the point cloud corresponding to each node need to be identified, segmented, and finally collapsed into a single point representing the node position. Automated point cloud identification and segmentation processes still remain a challenge in the industry, then, human intervention is always needed, resulting in a time-consuming process, normally involving tools that demand high computational power. Once the new point positions are determined, they are paired with the nodes in the as-design geometrical model to calculate their corresponding displacement. This process is repeated for sequential measurements with different loading conditions. Fig. 30 a) displays two superimposed sequential measurements and b) displays the final superimposed as-built models derived from the new node positions.

Figure 30. a) unloaded (purple) net pointcloud with identified nodes (red) superimposed to a loaded configuration (green) with identified nodes (blue). In b), the derived net configuration (points and lines) after processing the pointclouds.

From the unloaded node configuration of the net, a BIM model of the has been generated according to the IFC specification. Cable properties such as the sectional area, the current tension force, and the material information are defined in the model to be accessed by external computational agents dedicated to analysing its behavior.

A linear elastic structural analysis model has been established as defined in Ramonell et al. (2022). The model allows calculating the cable force configuration from the new point positions of the nodes of the net and its connectivity matrix. The model is fed with the material parameters defined in the BIM model and temperature measurements measured on-site. The calculation algorithm is encapsulated in a microservice to be integrated within the net digital twin ecosystem. The obtained tensional force distribution is used to update the information in the BIM model. The pipeline is depicted in Figure 31. Point clouds, derived node locations and tensional results are timestamped and stored within the ASHVIN digital twin platform in JSON format. Thus, the systematic upload of new point cloud measurements enables the acquisition of a performance history metrics for monitoring the evolution structural state of the net throughout its life.

Figure 31. Pipeline for updating cable force information from pointcloud measurements. In blue, information snippets that are stored in the ASHVIN platform. In orange, computational processes executed.

2.4 Disciplines:

Investigation discipline- risk assessment;

Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling

2.5 Life Cycle Stages: Production information and construction.

Section 3: Process-definition

*Life cycle stages: Construction stage
Production information and construction*

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

Figure 31 Exchange Requirements

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end

Section 6: References

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